

Studies on Indigoid Dyes. Part XII.

2-(4-Iodo) Thionaphthene-3'-Indole Indigos, 2-(4-Iodo) Thionaphthene-8'-Acenaphthylene Indigos and 2-(4/7-Iodo) Thionaphthene-1'-Aceanthrene Indigos

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Fourteen thioindigoid dyes have been prepared by the condensation of 4-iodothioindoxyl and 7-iodothioindoxyl (in two cases) with various ortho diketones. 4:4'-Diodothioindigo has also been prepared. The spectral and other properties of the dyes have been studied and compared with those of the isomeric 5-iodo, 6-iodo and 7-iodo substituted dyes.

THE present communication deals with the preparation and study of 4-iodothioindigoid dyes with the object of comparing these dyes with isomeric 5-iodo¹, 6-iodo² and 7-iodo³ thioindigoid dyes described earlier.

Seven dyes have been prepared by the condensation of 4-iodothioindoxyl⁴ with isatin and its substituted products. Another dye has been obtained by the condensation of 7-iodo-thioindoxyl⁵ with 5:7-dinitroisatin. These compounds have the general formula *K*.

- K_1 : 2-(4-Iodo) thionaphthene-3'-indole indigo.
- K_2 : 2-(4-Iodo) thionaphthene-3'-(5'-chloro) indole indigo.
- K_3 : 2-(4-Iodo) thionaphthene-3'-(5'-bromo) indole indigo.
- K_4 : 2-(4-Iodo) thionaphthene-3'-(5'-iodo) indole indigo.
- K_5 : 2-(4-Iodo) thionaphthene-3'-(5:7'-dibromo) indole indigo.
- K_6 : 2-(4-Iodo) thionaphthene-3'-(5'-bromo-7'-nitro) indole indigo.
- K_7 : 2-(4-Iodo) thionaphthene-3'-(5:7'-dinitro) indole indigo.
- K_8 : 2-(7-Iodo) thionaphthene-3'-(5:7'-dinitro) indole indigo.

A symmetrical thioindigoid dye 4:4'-diodothioindigo (*L*) has been prepared with a view to compare its properties with those of the isomeric symmetrical 5:5'-diodothioindigo⁵ reported earlier.

4-Iodothioindoxyl⁴ has been condensed with acenaphthenequinone and its substituted derivatives, and four new dyes have thus been prepared, represented by *M*.

- M_1 : 2-(4-Iodo) thionaphthene-8'-acenaphthylene indigo.
- M_2 : 2-(4-Iodo) thionaphthene-8'-(3'-chloro) acenaphthylene indigo.
- M_3 : 2-(4-Iodo) thionaphthene-8'-(3'-bromo) acenaphthylene indigo.
- M_4 : 2-(4-Iodo) thionaphthene-8'-(3':4'-dinitro) acenaphthylene indigo.

4-Iodo and 7-iodothioindoxyl have been condensed separately with aceanthrenequinone to produce two dyes, represented by *N*, with a view to study the influence of an additional benzene ring when fused to the ortho diketo compound of the reacting molecules.

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(N)

N₁ : 2-(4-Iodo) thionaphthene-1'-aceanthrene indigo.
 N₂ : 2-(7-Iodo) thionaphthene-1'-aceanthrene indigo.

The dyes currently reported are soluble in pyridine, aniline and nitrobenzene. The solution of the dyes in concentrated sulphuric acid produces characteristic colour and the original dyes are reprecipitated unchanged on dilution of the acid solutions. The dyeings on cotton were developed uniformly from an alkaline hydrosulphite vat at 50°-60°. The reduction of the dye K₁, however, required a higher temperature (80°-85°). The dyed shades on cotton and the colours in strong sulphuric acid of the dyes are given in Table 1.

The absorption maxima of these dyes were determined in pyridine solution with the help of a Hilger and Watts' spectrophotometer and these values together with log ε are shown in Table 1.

Table—1

T = Thionaphthene Dye 1	Shade on Cotton 2	AI = Acenaphthylene indigo Colour in Conc. H ₂ SO ₄ 3	II = Indole indigo λ _{max} in mμ 4	Log ε 5
2-(5-Iodo) T-3-II	Violet red	Light yellowish green	517.5	3.904
2-(4-Iodo) T-3-II	Violet red	Dark violet	504	3.997
2-(7-Iodo) T-3-II	Violet red	Violet	503	3.984
2-(6-Iodo) T-3-II	Violet red	Deep violet	500	3.905
2-(5-Iodo) T-3-(5'-Chloro) II	Violet red	Yellowish green	518	3.360
2-(4-Iodo) T-3-(5'-Chloro) II	Violet red	Deep violet	507	3.950
2-(7-Iodo) T-3-(5'-Chloro) II	Violet red	Violet	505	4.403
2-(6-Iodo) T-3-(5'-Chloro) II	Violet red	Deep violet	500	3.895
2-(5-Iodo) T-3-(5'-Bromo) II	Dark violet red	Yellowish green	519	3.408
2-(4-Iodo) T-3-(5'-Bromo) II	Reddish violet	Deep violet	507	3.920
2-(7-Iodo) T-3-(5'-Bromo) II	Violet red	Violet	505	4.058
2-(6-Iodo) T-3-(5'-Bromo) II	Deep violet red	Violet	500	3.957
2-(5-Iodo) T-3-(5'-Iodo) II	Reddish violet	Yellowish green	522	4.000
2-(4-Iodo) T-3-(5'-Iodo) II	Deep violet red	Deep violet	505	3.944
2-(7-Iodo) T-3-(5'-Iodo) II	Dark violet red	Violet	502	4.039
2-(6-Iodo) T-3-(5'-Iodo) II	Deep violet red	Violet	498	3.881
2-(5-Iodo) T-3-(5'-7'-dibromo) II	Dark violet red	Yellowish green	521	3.799
2-(4-Iodo) T-3-(5' : 7'-dibromo) II	Dark violet red	Violet	509	3.982
2-(7-Iodo) T-3-(5' : 7'-dibromo) II	Red	Dirty green	506	4.090
2-(6-Iodo) T-3-(5' : 7'-dibromo) II	Dark violet red	Deep violet	501	3.879
2-(5-Iodo) T-3-(5' : 7'-dinitro) II	Chocolate	Green	528	3.910
2-(4-Iodo) T-3-(5' : 7'-dinitro) II	Deep violet	Violet	514.5	3.980
2-(7-Iodo) T-3-(5' : 7'-dinitro) II	Chocolate	Blue violet	513	3.9225
2-(6-Iodo) T-3-(5' : 7'-dinitro) II	Deep chocolate	Reddish violet	512	3.922
2-(5-Iodo) T-3-(5'-bromo-7' nitro) II	Brownish red	Green	529	3.600
2-(4-Iodo) T-3-(5'-bromo-7' nitro) II	Reddish violet	Reddish violet	515	3.957
2-(7-Iodo) T-3-(5'-bromo-7' nitro) II	Dark red	Blue	502.5	4.352
2-(6-Iodo) T-3-(5'-bromo-7' nitro) II	Reddish brown	Light violet	510	4.010
5 : 5'-Diodo-thioindigo	Reddish violet (Pink)	Green	566	3.175
4 : 4'-Diodo-thioindigo	Reddish violet	Green	552	4.231
7 : 7'-Diodo-thioindigo	Reddish violet	Green	550	4.163
6 : 6'-Diodo-thioindigo	Reddish violet	Violet	543	3.455
2-(5-Iodo) T-8'-AI	Orange red	Green	527.5	4.259
2-(7-Iodo) T-8'-AI	Reddish violet	Green	518	4.054
2-(4-Iodo) T-8'-AI	Orange red	Green	516	4.024
2-(6-Iodo) T-8'-AI	Red	Green	515	4.000
2-(5-Iodo) T-8'-(3'-chloro) AI	Violet red	Green	528	4.360
2-(7-Iodo) T-8'-(3'-chloro) AI	Reddish violet	Green	520	4.080
2-(4-Iodo) T-8'-(3'-chloro) AI	Violet red	Green	516.5	4.034
2-(6-Iodo) T-8'-(3'-chloro) AI	Reddish violet	Green	515.5	4.007
2-(5-Iodo) T-8'-(3'-bromo) AI	Orange red	Olive green	528	4.116
2-(7-Iodo) T-8'-(3'-bromo) AI	Reddish violet	Green	520	4.089
2-(4-Iodo) T-8'-(3'-bromo) AI	Reddish violet	Deep green	519	4.055
2-(6-Iodo) T-8'-(3'-bromo) AI	Reddish violet	Green	518	4.066
2-(5-Iodo) T-8'-(3' : 4'-dinitro) AI	Blackish brown	Dirty brown	532	4.597
2-(7-Iodo) T-8'-(3' : 4'-dinitro) AI	Dark reddish violet	Green	522	4.035
2-(4-Iodo) T-8'-(3' : 4'-dinitro) AI	Chocolate	Reddish violet	520	4.081
2-(6-Iodo) T-8'-(3' : 4'-dinitro) AI	Greenish brown	Violet	512	3.700
2-(5-Iodo) T-1'-aceanthrene indigo	Reddish brown	Dirty greenish brown	513	3.944
2-(7-Iodo) T-1'-aceanthrene indigo	Reddish violet	Green	492	3.905
2-(4-Iodo) T-1'-aceanthrene indigo	Reddish violet	Brown	491	3.903
2-(6-Iodo) T-1'-aceanthrene indigo	Pink	Violet	490	3.884

TABLE 2

Dye	Reactants	Appearance	Yield	M. P.	Formula	Analysis	
						% Found	% Reqd.
S = 4-Iodothioindoxyl							
K₁	Isatin(0.184 g.) + S(0.345 g.) + AcOH(10ml)	Small needles	0.44 g., 87%	> 315°	C ₁₆ H ₉ O ₃ NSI	I:31.29 S: 7.85 Cl: 8.05	31.40 7.90 8.10
K₂	5-Chloroisatin(0.272 g.) + S(0.414 g.) + AcOH(15 ml.)	Small needles	0.55 g., 83.3%	> 315°	C ₁₆ H ₇ O ₂ NSCl	I:29.00 S: 7.25 Br:16.6	28.90 7.30 16.50
K₃	5-Bromoisatin(0.339 g.) + S(0.414 g.) + AcOH(15 ml.)	Small needles	0.6 g., 82.6%	> 315°	C ₁₆ H ₇ O ₂ NSBr	I:26.10 S: 6.57 I:47.78	26.20 6.61 47.83
K₄	5-Iodoisatin(0.41 g.) + S(0.414 g.) + AcOH(27 ml.)	Bundles of small stout needles	0.6 g., 75.4%	> 315°	C ₁₆ H ₇ O ₂ NSI ₂	S: 6.1	6.02
K₅	5:7-Dibromoisatin(0.169 g.) + S(0.153 g.) + AcOH(9 ml.)	Clusters of small needles	0.29 g., 92.9%	> 315°	C ₁₆ H ₆ O ₂ NSBr ₂ I	Br:28.25 I:22.50	28.40 22.60
K₆	5-Bromo-7-nitroisatin(0.406 g.) + S(0.414 g.) + AcOH(15 ml.)	Star shaped crystals(small)	0.67 g., 84.5%	> 315°	C ₁₆ H ₆ O ₄ N ₂ SBrI	S: 5.65 Br:15.15 I:24.00	5.70 15.10 24.14
K₇	5:7-Dinitroisatin (0.355 g.) + S(0.414 g.) + AcOH(14 ml.)	Small fine needles	0.63 g., 84.9%	> 315°	C ₁₆ H ₆ O ₆ N ₃ SI	S: 5.90 I:25.70	6.00 25.65
K₈	5:7-Dinitroisatin(0.266 g.) + S(0.338 g.) + AcOH(10 ml.)	Granular crystals	0.43 g., 71%	> 300°	C ₁₆ H ₆ O ₆ N ₃ SI	S: 6.50 I:25.60	6.46 25.65
M₁	Acenaphthenequinone(0.273 g.) + S(0.414 g.) + AcOH(20 ml.)	Long stout needles	0.51 g., 76%	272°-73°	C ₂₀ H ₉ O ₂ SI	S: 6.51 I:28.80	6.46 28.86
M₂	3-Chloroacenaphthenequinone(0.361 g.) + S(0.46 g.) + AcOH(20 ml.)	Granular crystals	0.32 g., 40.5%	275°-76° (Shrinking at 269°C)	C ₂₀ H ₈ O ₂ SCH	S: 7.20 Cl: 7.20 I:26.80	7.27 7.48 26.70
M₃	3 ^o Bromoacena phthenequinone (0.392 g) + S(0.414 g.) + AcOH (20 ml.)	Small needles	0.63 g., 80.9%	269°	C ₂₀ H ₈ O ₂ SBrI	Br+I:39.7	39.88
M₄	3:4-Dinitroacenaphthenequinone(0.272 g) + S(0.276 g.) + AcOH(45 ml.)	Granular crystals	0.26 g., 49%	> 310°	C ₂₀ H ₇ O ₆ N ₂ SI	S: 6.10 I:23.90	6.16 23.96
N₁	Acenaphthenequinone(0.135 g.) + S(0.161 g.) + AcOH(15 ml.)	Clusters of granular crystals	0.2 g., 69.9%	> 300°	C ₂₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ SI	S: 5.90 I:26.05	6.03 25.91
N₂	Acenaphthenequinone(0.232 g.) + S ₁ (0.276 g.) + AcOH(32 ml.)	Foliated needles	0.28 g., 57.1%	> 300°	C ₂₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ SI	S: 6.50 I:25.83	6.53 25.91

The order of absorption maxima for the iodo substituent at the various positions of the thionaphthene ring follows the same order as in the case of the thioindigos. Iodo substituent at the 5-position gives the highest absorption maxima in this series while the iodo substituent at positions 4 and 7 are generally somewhat similar, that of 4-iodo compounds being slightly higher than those of 7-iodo hemithioindirubines. The wavelength of absorption maxima for 6-iodo compounds is generally lowest of all the four different iodo compounds. It is only in 2-(iodo) thionaphthene-3'-(5'-bromo-7'-nitro) indole indigo that the iodo substituent at the 6-position has a larger absorption maxima than the compound with the iodo group at position 7. An explanation which can be given for this change in the order of the absorption maxima is that in this compound there is probably considerable hydrogen bonding between the oxygen of the $-\text{NO}_2$ group at the 7'-position with the hydrogen attached to the N atom of the indole ring. This hydrogen bonding may induce orientation of the nitro group to set it co-planar with that of the aromatic ring, leading to extension of the π -electrons.

Electronegativity of N being higher than that of S, substituents in the indole ring generally produces a comparatively slight effect on the absorption maxima of the hemithioindirubines. It is only when there are more than one substituent on the indole ring, that is when the probability for resonance in the aromatic ring is much more increased, that the absorption maxima rises. Even then the hemithioindirubines have a smaller absorption maxima than the thioindigos.

In all these dyes the iodo substituent at position 5 in the dye molecule, a position of maximum charge density (being at the end of the aromatic conjugated system), produces a maximum bathochromic effect on the wavelength of the absorption maxima. While the iodo substituted at position 6 in the dye molecule has the lowest (except in one single example) wavelength of absorption compared to the iodo substituent at any other position of the thionaphthene ring system. These general trends in the absorption maxima agrees well with the properties of the ring system of the indigo dyes. The electronegativity and size of the heteroatom involved, undoubtedly play an important role in determining the order of the wavelength of absorption maxima of the related dye molecules. A large iodo substituent at the position 7 produces an absorption maxima comparable (slightly less) to the effect produced by the substituent at position 4 of the thioindigo dyes.

The absorption of the 2-(iodo) thionaphthene-8'-acenaphthylene indigos are listed in Table 1. The order of absorption maxima for the iodo substituent at various positions in the thionaphthene is different from that observed for the thioindigos and hemithioindirubines. The order decreases as follows : $5 > 7 > 4 > 6$.

In Table I the absorption maxima for the iodo derivatives of 2-thionaphthene-1'-aceanthrene indigos are given. The order of the absorption maxima for the iodo substituents at the four different positions of the thionaphthene ring is of the same order $5 > 7 > 4 > 6$ as in the preceding 2-(iodo) thionaphthene-8'-acenaphthylene indigos. This class of arene thioindigos having quite a low absorption maxima usually produces a lighter shade on cotton than most of the other indigo dyes studied.

Experimental

Dye (L) 4:4'-Diodothioindigo : 4-Iodothioindoxyl (0.7 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (100 ml., 2 N). Potassium ferricyanide solution (5%) was added dropwise till no further precipitate appeared and the resulting mixture heated on a water-bath for 1 hr. The violet red dye (0.45 g.) was filtered and recrystallised from nitrobenzene in star shaped crystals, m. p. $> 300^\circ$.

(Found I, 46.13 ; S, 11.70 ; $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{S}_2\text{I}_2$ requires I, 46.35 ; S, 11.67 per cent).

Preparation of other Thioindigoid Dyes : Isatin or acenaphthenequinone or aceanthrenequinone was dissolved in boiling glacial acetic acid and equimolecular proportion of iodothioindoxyl was added. The resulting solution on treatment with HCl (Conc., 2 - 3 ml.) precipitated the dye. The mixture was boiled for 10 to 15 min, filtered while hot, and the residue washed with a little acetic acid and hot water. The dyes were recrystallised from either xylene or nitrobenzene.

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